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Assessment of Physical Characteristics of Carbonized Mahogany Sawdust (*Toona calantas*) as Charcoal Briquettes

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Abstract

The present study aims to the feasibility and potential application of briquettes obtained from dehydrated mahogany sawdust as a feasible and eco-friendly alternative to traditional fuels. Briquettes have been observed to be widely utilized in rural areas for culinary purposes. These briquettes are derived from various biomass sources, which contribute to the reduction of carbon emissions and the promotion of ecological consciousness in waste management and energy generation. Lantawan Municipality of Basilan, renowned for its agricultural resources, such mahogany lumber and sawdust as substantial agricultural wastes that can be potential to the production of biofuel. Notably, CMS exhibits favorable characteristics for briquette manufacturing, owing to its capacity for carbon sequestration, durability, efficiency, burning time, kindling time, and heat quality. This study aims to assess the physical characteristics, efficacy, and combustion time of CMS charcoal briquettes by means of a Likert questionnaire. Results revealed a cumulative average rating of 5.0 (Very Much liked) in all parameters expressing high praise for the briquettes' remarkable capacity. Although CMS briquettes performed well in all physical tests, proving their viability as an eco-friendly energy source, recommendation such as collection and transformation of mahogany sawdust into sustainable alternative biomass fuel, Enhancement of the efficiency and accessibility by involving Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) students in the design and creation of machines that could optimize the production process and testing briquettes to various parameters such as fixed carbon content, moisture content, and ash content to improve product yields and performances.

Keywords: *briquettes, biofuel, capstone, proximate analysis, sustainable development*

Introduction

Agriculture serves as the primary means of economic sustenance, particularly in the region of Basilan. One of Basilan's primary commodities encompasses copra, rubber, coffee, and other related items. In addition, it is worth noting that Basilan offers various livelihood opportunities, including the production of charcoal, furniture, and wood lumber. During the course of furniture and tree cutting operations, a byproduct known as sawdust is generated. Sawdust is frequently regarded as a superfluous material and is frequently subjected to combustion. In a recent study, researchers have devised a methodology to transform sawdust into a viable form of biomass. The mahogany tree is frequently employed in the production of furniture due to its notable attributes as a sustainable wood. These include its capacity for carbon sequestration, extended product lifespan, and the potential benefits associated with recycling, as highlighted by AKD Furniture. Mahogany, scientifically known as *Swietenia*, is a highly durable wood species that exhibits rapid growth and is frequently utilized in the production of furniture and construction materials (Daray, 2011). Mahogany is a magnificent and aesthetically pleasing tree that represents power and resilience. According to Forest Generation (2020), the subject under investigation exhibits notable protective attributes and has been recognized for its capacity to endure lightning strikes. The utilization of mahogany as a viable substitute for biomass briquettes has been observed.

Basically, the conversion of waste materials, specifically sawdust, into high-density and energy-efficient briquettes can be achieved through the process of densification. The process of densifying biomass into briquettes has emerged as a promising renewable energy alternative to conventional fossil fuels, as highlighted by Pallo et al. (2020). The utilization of mahogany sawdust in the production of briquettes was deemed appropriate by the researcher. According to Dinisha et al. (2019), biomass briquettes have the potential to effectively address the energy requirements associated with cooking and heating, particularly in rural regions characterized by ample biomass feedstock. The process of briquetting involves subjecting raw materials to high pressure, resulting in the liberation of lignin from wood or biomass. This liberation of lignin facilitates the binding of the material into a cohesive briquette structure. The optimal water content in the raw material for briquetting exhibits variability and is contingent upon the specific characteristics of the raw material (Nikolaisen & Jensen, 2013). Briquettes have emerged as a prevalent renewable energy material, effectively addressing the issue of excessive reliance on wood fuel as a primary energy source for human consumption. The performance of these materials is contingent upon the specific types and characteristics of binders employed throughout the preparation and densification procedures. (Olugbade et al., 2019). As per Fote Machinery's report in 2023, charcoal briquettes are a form of fuel derived from charcoal powder. In contrast to conventional fuels, charcoal briquettes exhibit the advantageous characteristics of continuous heat generation and the absence of smoke and odor during combustion. Hence, it has garnered significant traction in both domestic and industrial sectors, emerging as the prevailing fuel choice in numerous nations including Kenya, the Middle East, Uganda, India, and others. The study was undertaken by the researchers with the intention of investigating the potential utility of mahogany tree sawdust derived from furniture production and tree cutting. The objective was to explore the feasibility of converting this sawdust into an alternative biomass fuel, as opposed to its conventional combustion. The primary objective of the researcher is to transform mahogany sawdust into charcoal

briquettes.

Moreover, the local population in Basilan relies heavily on agriculture as their main economic source of income. Notable exports include copra, rubber, coffee, and other products. Moreover, the production of charcoal, the manufacturing of furniture, and the harvesting of natural wood timber offer alternative avenues for generating livelihoods. The byproduct of tree chopping and furniture production, known as sawdust, is commonly regarded as waste and subsequently incinerated. A study has been devised by researchers to investigate the conversion of sawdust into a viable alternative form of biomass. Mahogany trees are commonly employed in the manufacturing of furniture owing to their notable characteristics, including their expeditious growth, ability to sequester carbon, extended lifespan of products, and recyclability (AKD Furniture). According to Daray (2011), mahogany (*Swietenia*) is a hardwood that is renowned for its durability and aesthetic appeal, making it a popular choice for furniture and construction materials. According to Forest Generation (2020), mahogany trees, which are often associated with strength and power, exhibit remarkable resilience, even when confronted with lightning strikes. The utilization of mahogany sawdust as a viable option for biomass briquette production is evident. The process of densification enables the conversion of sawdust into briquettes that exhibit enhanced density and improved energy efficiency. As per the findings of Kpalo et al. (2020), the process of densifying biomass into briquettes presents a viable renewable energy alternative to conventional fossil fuels. Researchers were inspired to produce briquettes using mahogany sawdust. According to Dinesha et al. (2019), biomass briquettes have been identified as a viable solution for addressing energy requirements related to cooking and heating, particularly in rural regions that possess ample biomass feedstock. In addition, Briquetting is a process that entails subjecting raw material to elevated pressure, resulting in the liberation of lignin present in wood or biomass. This lignin then serves to bind the material together, forming solid briquettes. The significance of the water content of the raw material in achieving successful briquetting is underscored by Nikolaisen and Jensen (2013). Briquettes play a pivotal role in the realm of renewable energy, effectively mitigating reliance on wood fuel and effectively tackling the concomitant environmental concerns. The performance of briquettes is contingent upon the specific type and inherent characteristics of binders employed during the processes of preparation and densification, as elucidated by Olugbade et al. (2019). According to Fote Machinery (2023), charcoal briquettes, which are produced by combining charcoal powder with binders, have gained popularity in various countries such as Kenya, the Middle East, Uganda, and India due to their ability to generate continuous heat without emitting smoke or odor. Charcoal briquettes have gained significant traction in various domains, encompassing both domestic and industrial sectors. The objective of this study is to explore the potential of repurposing sawdust derived from mahogany tree furniture production and tree felling as a sustainable biomass fuel, as opposed to conventional combustion methods. The main aim of this study is to convert mahogany sawdust into charcoal briquettes, thereby offering a viable and environmentally friendly energy alternative.

Methodology

Research Design

The experimental design used in this work is an exploratory one. It is possible to define exploratory research as a form of research design in which research is carried out with the purpose of gaining a deeper understanding of an issue that is not clearly defined. In order to collect information, the researchers will only carry out a physical examination of the briquettes and will make use of a survey questionnaire on the subject. The use of Likert scale will be employed to examine evaluators' satisfaction/observation towards the created briquettes. Additionally, the researchers will investigate the published literature concerning briquette technique as well as the quantity of biomass that is not being utilized. Both the utilization of biomass and the establishment of one-of-a-kind processes that are tailored to the availability of organic wastes have been extensively documented.

Materials Used and Procedures

In addition to the Mahogany Sawdusts that were collected as part of the biomass materials. The following items were utilized in the research project: a PVC pipe measuring 28 centimeters, a container or bowl, a pan and stove, and a mesh sieve measuring 120. Balance has three beams and a graduated cylinder. Cornstarch is the primary binder that is used in studies. Because of the design, it is necessary to devise a method that makes use of the digital and printed resources that are already available. In the course of this investigation, the emphasis is placed on the actual application of the hypothesized procedure in order to ascertain whether or not it is feasible. In this stage, we will be executing a straightforward design and trial procedure in order to build a briquette formulation that is more applicable to real-world situations. 750 grams of pulverized biomass, 2 liters of water, and 500 grams of starch were the basic ingredients that were necessary for the mahogany briquettes recipe in this investigation. Forty briquettes may be produced with this mixture. The amount of time required for carbonization is contingent upon the amount of biomass that is present. For instance, a batch of one sack of dried mahogany sawdust required three to four hours of regulated fire and conditions in order to be produced. After the carbonization process is complete, the material is crushed by passing it through a sieve with a 120-mesh opening. The starch and water should be mixed together in a saucepan until the starch is completely dissolved. The wet mixture should be heated over medium heat and stirred until it reaches a sticky consistency. To achieve the desired uniformity, it will take around four to five minutes to reach that point. Subsequent to the completion of the combination, gradually incorporate the crushed biomass until it reaches the appropriate consistency, which is neither excessively dry nor excessively high in moisture. After that, the process of compaction consisted of introducing wood into the carbonized biomass and utilizing PVC as a mold to further compact the material. To ensure that the material is well compacted, apply firm pressure with your palm. After applying the product, it was necessary to allow it to dry for a period of

twelve hours while it was exposed to heat. The following is the general steps involved in the formation of the briquette are listed below.

Figure 1. General steps in the development of CMS briquettes

Evaluation of Physical Characteristics of CMS Briquettes

The researchers will select three respondents, including a housewife, a seller, and a charcoal vendor, in order to evaluate the carbonized rice hull briquettes in terms of their durability, efficiency, kindling time, burning time, and heating quality. Before making use of the carbonized briquettes, the student researchers will first provide an introduction to the components that were utilized in their manufacturing, and then they will proceed to provide guidance on how to make appropriate use of the units. The performance of the generated briquettes will be compared with that of ordinary charcoal, and the level of acceptability of the product will be evaluated using a hedonic rating scale (see table 1 for more information). The capacity of the briquettes to survive damage when subjected to external pressures is referred to as their durability. The responders will make an evaluation of the briquettes' durability by determining the ease with which they may be broken down. b) Efficiency: one of the most important aspects of the briquette is its efficacy. A determination is made regarding the rate at which it is able to bring the water to a boil. The briquettes would be used for culinary purposes by the participants, and they would pay close attention to the rate at which the briquettes brought the food to a boil. The rate at which the briquettes catch fire is determined by the Ignition Speed, which is an important factor. The respondents will pay close attention to the briquettes as they are lit in order to identify the rate at which they ignite and whether or not they ignite slowly. d) Burning Time: This factor defines how long the product will burn while it is being utilized properly. After the briquettes have been ignited, the responders will evaluate them, taking into consideration the length of time they produce heat and how long they last when they are in use. e) Heating Quality: This factor is crucial in determining the amount of heat that is generated by the briquettes. The respondents will evaluate the heat that is produced by the briquettes and judge whether or not the briquettes are effective for the purpose of heating in the environment.

Table 1. Scale for the Acceptability Level of Each physical Characteristic of the CMS briquettes

Scale	Interval	Degree of Response
5	4.20 - 5.00	Liked Very Much
4	3.40 - 4.19	Liked Moderately
3	2.60 - 3.39	Neither Liked nor Disliked
2	1.80 - 2.59	Disliked Moderately
1	1.00 -1.79	Disliked Very Much

Results and Discussion

The table presented below illustrates the outcomes of the physical assessment conducted on mahogany sawdust briquettes. In the course of the interview, the initial step involved the evaluation of durability as a primary method of assessment. In order to evaluate the durability of the subject under investigation, a drop test was conducted, wherein each participant underwent three trials. The participants emphasized the hardness of the briquettes and conveyed contentment regarding their long-lasting nature. According to the participants, it was asserted that Carbonized Mahogany Sawdust (CMS) briquettes possess the inherent ability to elevate water temperature to its boiling point. In order to conduct the experiment, three standard cups of water were poured into a pan. The participants expressed their

admiration for the efficacy of the CMS briquettes, specifically their capacity to rapidly elevate the temperature of water and achieve boiling point within a mere 14-minute timeframe. The positive feedback regarding the rapid boiling capacity of mahogany sawdust charcoal briquettes has substantiated their potential as a feasible and ecologically sustainable energy alternative. The participants' feedback regarding the briquettes' rapid ignition and fire adaptability was overwhelmingly positive. The researchers were duly impressed by the remarkable rapidity with which the briquettes exhibited ignition, attaining ignition within a mere 1.5 minutes of fire contact. In the course of conducting the burning time test, participants observed that the burning time exhibited by the mahogany sawdust charcoal briquettes was notably remarkable. The researchers made an intriguing observation regarding the duration of combustion, noting that a total burning time of 50 minutes was recorded for 15 briquettes. The participants emphasized the convenience and efficiency of the heat duration of the briquettes.

Table 2. Evaluation of physical Characteristics of the CMS Briquettes

<i>Sensory Characteristics</i>	<i>Rate</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Durability	5.0	Liked Very Much
Efficiency	5.0	Liked Very Much
Kindling Time	5.0	Liked Very Much
Burning Time	5.0	Liked Very Much
Heating Quality	5.0	Liked Very Much
General Average Rating	5.0	Liked Very Much

Conclusions

Reusing mahogany sawdust as biomass is an innovative renewable energy strategy. Waste to energy is a clever way to assist the community and provide sustainable electricity. Researchers turned mahogany sawdust into charcoal briquettes to generate sustainable energy instead of discarding or burning it. Results and comments indicate effective evaluation of Carbonized Mahogany Sawdust (CMS) briquette performance, including durability, efficiency, kindling time, burning time, and heating quality, using the Likert scale from three evaluators. Every feature of the CMS briquettes received good scores and favorable feedback from respondents, suggesting satisfaction. The answers said CMS briquettes are hard, thus they can withstand handling and transit. The CMS briquettes' capacity to swiftly heat water and boil it impressed respondents. Participants also liked the fast igniting and fire adjustability of the kindling time. The CMS briquettes' outstanding burning time demonstrated their simplicity and efficiency. The tremendous heat generated by the heating system was well accepted. Carbonized Mahogany Sawdust briquettes performed well in all tests, proving their viability as an eco-friendly energy source. With these, part of our recommendation, is the collection of mahogany sawdust and subsequent transformation into briquettes presents which may promising opportunity for the community to derive substantial advantages, thereby offering a sustainable alternative biomass fuel. Enhancing the efficiency and accessibility of mahogany sawdust briquettes can be achieved by involving Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) students in the design and creation of machines that optimize the production process. In order to enhance the performance of the briquettes, it is recommended that future researchers delve into various parameters, including but not limited to fixed carbon content, moisture content, and ash content. The implementation of this collaborative approach serves to not only advance environmental sustainability but also cultivate local innovation and education, thereby facilitating the development of a dependable and environmentally conscious energy solution.

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